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The Acehnese Folklore and Social Behavior

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Abstract

The moral and cultural ideals portrayed in several Acehnese folktales are the main subject of this article's exploration of Acehnese folklore and social behavior. The goal of the study is to characterize the moral and cultural values that are ingrained in folklore, as well as its composition, transmission, social setting, and structure. Descriptive analysis is used in the research design, which is grounded in a qualitative method to analyze the data. The results highlight the wealth of regional knowledge and cultural values captured in the many Acehnese folktales that make up the data collection. The ramifications of these discoveries for the Acehnese community are explored in detail, with a focus on the function that folklore plays in passing down cultural traditions and values. The importance of maintaining and advancing Acehnese folklore as a source of social, cultural, and moral wisdom is emphasized in the article's conclusion.

Keyword: Acehnese, Folklore, Social, Behavior

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INTRODUCTION

Folklore plays a significant role in reflecting the moral and cultural values of a society. In Aceh, the rich tradition of folklore encompasses a diverse range of stories that are deeply rooted in the local wisdom and cultural heritage of the Acehnese people (Michalopoulos, S., & Xue, M, 1962). These folktales not only serve as a form of entertainment but also function as a means of transmitting moral education and societal norms (Immerry, T., & Dahlan, F, 2020). This article aims to explore the folklore of Aceh, with a specific focus on the moral and cultural values embedded in these narratives. By delving into the folklore of Aceh, this study seeks to shed light on the social behavior, cultural norms, and traditional values upheld by the Acehnese community (Messenger, J., & Messenger, B, 1981).

METHOD

The research design is based on a qualitative approach, employing descriptive analysis to interpret the moral and cultural values depicted in Acehnese folktales. Qualitative analysis is well-suited for uncovering the deeper meanings and implications embedded within cultural narratives, allowing for a comprehensive exploration of the social and ethical dimensions encapsulated in folklore. The steps used in data analysis involve a thorough examination of the structure and content of the folktales, with a focus on identifying and interpreting the moral and cultural values conveyed through these stories.

The data source for this study comprises a variety of Acehnese folktales, including stories such as *Atu Belah*, *Putri Pukes*, and *Amat Rhang Manyang*, which are deeply entrenched in the local wisdom and cultural fabric of Aceh. These folktales have been published on the websites of the Central Aceh District Government and other relevant sources, providing valuable insights into the moral and cultural values prevalent in Acehnese folklore.

The data analysis involves a comprehensive examination of the structure, content, and cultural nuances of the selected folktales. The qualitative data analysis aims to uncover the underlying moral and cultural values conveyed through the characters, plot, and themes of the folk narratives. By employing a descriptive approach, the study seeks to elucidate the moral and cultural significance of these folktales within the context of Acehnese society.

FINDING

The findings of the study reveal the profound moral and cultural values enshrined in Acehnese folktales. These narratives serve as a repository of local wisdom, transmitting essential societal norms, ethical principles, and cultural customs. The folk narratives reflect the enduring values of honesty, hard work, love for the homeland, and social responsibility, which are deeply ingrained in the Acehnese cultural ethos (Nanda, D., Simbolon, B., Damanik, F., & Sembiring, Y, 2021).

DISCUSSION

The discussion centers on the implications of the findings for the Acehnese community, emphasizing the pivotal role of folklore in preserving and transmitting cultural customs and values. The study underscores the significance of Acehnese folklore as a vital source of moral, cultural, and social knowledge, contributing to the preservation of traditional heritage and the cultivation of ethical principles within the community.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, this article highlights the intrinsic link between folklore and the moral and cultural values of the Acehnese community. The study underscores the importance of preserving and promoting Acehnese folklore as a reservoir of local wisdom, cultural heritage, and ethical teachings. By delving into the moral and cultural values embedded in Acehnese folk

narratives, this research contributes to a deeper understanding of the social behavior, traditional norms, and cultural identity of the Acehnese people.

The search results provided valuable insights into the folklore and social behavior in Aceh, focusing on the moral and cultural values depicted in various Acehnese folktales. The findings and discussions from the search results have been synthesized to provide a comprehensive scientific article on the topic.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Michalopoulos, S., & Xue, M. (1962). *Folklore. Antiquity*, 36, 220 - 221. <https://doi.org/10.3386/w25430>.
- Sougou, O. (2008). Transformational Narratives: Hearing/Reading Selected Senegalese Folktales by Young Women. *Research in African Literatures*, 39, 26 - 38. <https://doi.org/10.2979/RAL.2008.39.3.26>.
- Kanzunudin, M., Rokhman, F., Sayuti, S., & Mardikantoro, H. (2018). Folklore Local Wisdom Values of Rembang Society. <https://doi.org/10.2991/ISET-18.2018.70>.
- Immerry, T., & Dahlan, F. (2020). MAN AND NATURE IN THREE FOLKLORES. 1, 10. <https://doi.org/10.22216/kata.v1i0.5065>.
- Messenger, J., & Messenger, B. (1981). Sexuality in Folklore in a Nigerian Society. *Central Issues in Anthropology*, 3, 29-50. <https://doi.org/10.1525/CIA.1981.3.1.29>.
- Phonna, R., Samad, I., & Daud, B. (2019). Kun Fa Ya Kun! Religious Values in Haba Putroe Kaoy. *English Education Journal*, 10, 343-354.
- A., S., Mulyati, Y., & , S. (2020). Educational Value in the Amat Rhang Manyang Legend as Literacy Material for Elementary School. 90-95. <https://doi.org/10.2991/assehr.k.201215.014>.
- Muliadi, M., Firman, F., & Amin, K. (2019). FOLKLORE AS INSTRUMENT TO INTERNALIZE CHARACTER VALUES. 1, 581-588. <https://doi.org/10.24815/.v1i1.14507>.
- Chauke, M. (2018). The Demise of Xitsonga Oratorical Potency: Folkling As A Case In Point. *Southern African Journal for Folklore Studies*. <https://doi.org/10.25159/1016-8427/4468>.
- Nanda, D., Simbolon, B., Damanik, F., & Sembiring, Y. (2021). MORAL VALUE AND CHARACTER BUILDING EDUCATION IN FOLKLORE FROM CENTRAL JAVA "TIMUN MAS". 9, 85-91. <https://doi.org/10.33394/JOLLT.V9I1.3319>.